

Flame structure study of premixed NH₃/O₂/Ar flames using Raman spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT

While NH₃ has gained a lot of interest as a potential carbon-free fuel, at present, there are notable disagreements when it comes to predictions of some of its combustion characteristics, such as burning velocity or species mole fractions, in particular of NO_x, which have the potential to cause significant harm to both human health and the environment. Nevertheless, because the NH₃ flame presents multiple challenges for experimental studies, there is a lack of data that could assist with the further development of kinetic models. In the present work, the authors demonstrate enhanced Raman spectroscopy with multiple laser beam passages that allows for non-intrusive sensitive detection and quantification of two nitrogen oxide species, NO and N₂O, in flame with detection limits of 600 and 500 ppm, respectively. All the datasets were acquired in NH₃/O₂/Ar flames, to only involve NO_x reactions from fuel-bound nitrogen, at three equivalence ratios ($\Phi=0.8, 1.0, 1.2$). The processed datasets were compared with predictions of four chemical kinetic mechanisms and possible reasons for disagreements in model predictions were discussed. While overall model performance varies between different flames, most of the models tested give acceptable predictions for the NO profiles, with predictions of all models being on the lower end of the experimental data range for rich flames. For N₂O, the obtained peak mole fraction values of 1670 ($\Phi=0.8$), 1060 ($\Phi=1.0$) and 670 ($\Phi=1.2$) ppm have been well reproduced by one of the models within the experimental error margins.

Novelty and significance statement

The current work presents the first quantitative non-intrusive measurements of N₂O, an important combustion intermediate, in NH₃ flames. Paired with additional flame structure data on NO and major species mole fractions, and temperature, the acquired data has the potential to assist with the development of kinetic models of NH₃ combustion. The obtained results are also compared with four recent kinetic mechanisms and their performance is assessed.

1. Introduction

Massive research efforts during recent years were devoted to the advancement of combustion technologies for ammonia (NH₃) as a carbon-free energy vector. Although ammonia has unfavorable combustion properties compared to traditional hydrocarbon fuels, they can

be overcome using different approaches such as mixing with more reactive fuels, e.g. hydrogen produced by partial dissociation of NH₃, or other alternative fuels. Nevertheless, a critical problem in ammonia combustion is the unavoidable formation of nitrogen oxides. For instance, the formation of N₂O and NO₂ observed in the exhaust of ammonia-fueled SI engines [1] can easily offset any advantages of NH₃ being carbon-free since N₂O is a much more potent greenhouse gas than CO₂ [2].

Mitigating the formation of nitrogen oxides and optimizing the performance of practical combustion devices operated with ammonia requires a detailed understanding of combustion chemistry and the development of reliable chemical kinetic models for combustion simulations. It is, therefore, alarming to observe significant differences between available experimental data on the structure of NH₃ flames and predictions of recent kinetic mechanisms. For example, Osipova et al. [3] measured major and minor species profiles in NH₃/H₂/O₂/Ar flames at 4 and 6 atm using molecular beam mass-spectrometry and compared them with predictions of eight recently developed kinetic models. While the profiles of major species, NH₃, H₂, O₂, N₂ and H₂O were well

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reproduced, predictions of NO profiles showed mixed results, where some models significantly over- or under-predicted NO formation. Moreover, all models significantly overpredicted maximum concentrations of N_2O and NO_2 in lean, stoichiometric, and rich flames; only the mechanism by Zhang et al. [4] approached measured profiles at some conditions considering notable experimental uncertainties. Similar discrepancies were also observed by Osipova et al. [5] at atmospheric pressure in $NH_3/O_2/Ar$ and $NH_3/H_2/O_2/Ar$ flames.

Osipova et al. [3,5] reported that the experimental uncertainty of major species concentrations was $\pm 20\%$, while for NO_x it was $\pm 50\%$ and emphasized the need for further studies of nitrogen chemistry in ammonia flames. Therefore, the primary goal of the present work was to provide an independent experimental dataset on the structure of pre-mixed $NH_3/O_2/Ar$ flames.

Laser-diagnostic methods possess a variety of advantages for flame studies [6–8], in particular, the possibility to perform non-intrusive measurements *in situ*, which is of most importance for the validation of chemical kinetic models [9]. Quantitative laser-diagnostic studies in NH_3 flames have previously been performed with laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) and Coherent Anti-Stokes Raman Spectroscopy (CARS), e. g. [10–17]. However, this methodology requires consecutive measurements with different techniques to enable mole fraction and temperature data acquisition.

Contrary to that, Raman spectroscopy [18] allows for simultaneous detection and quantification of the chemical composition, as well as temperature measurements. Previous studies of NH_3 flame structure using Raman spectroscopy [19–22] were focused on measurements of major species and nitric oxide present in the product zone. In the present work, spatial profiles of N_2O , a combustion intermediate, were obtained in addition to the determination of O_2 , N_2 , NH_3 , H_2O , H_2 , NO and temperature. Laser-diagnostic studies of N_2O are scarce and have primarily been limited to non-combustion measurements with line-of-sight absorption spectroscopy [23] and rotational CARS [24]. Lill et al. recently presented a development of Raman spectroscopy targeting measurements of N_2O in flames and also included a qualitative profile of N_2O in a pre-mixed $NH_3/H_2/N_2$ -air flame stabilized in an opposed-jet burner configuration [25]. The present study provides an independent data set to address the issues on NH_3 flame modeling discussed above and, to the best of the authors' knowledge, represents the first quantitative laser-based measurements of N_2O in flame.

2. Experimental details

2.1. Experimental setup

The setup employed in the current experiment is based on a multipass system, variations of which have been recently successfully applied to enhance the relatively weak Raman signals [26,27] to allow for the detection of minor species. A similar system, operating at 532 nm excitation wavelength, has been used in our previous work [28].

Fig. 1. a) Schematic of the experimental setup. M: mirror, WP: half-wave plate, SL: spherical lens, SM: spherical mirror, AL: achromatic lens, BM: broadband mirror, F: 355 nm notch filter. b) A photo of the multipass arrangement.

However, operation at 532 nm wavelength in NH_3 flames leads to LIF, which produces a background signal strong enough to obscure Raman signals, eliminating any possibility of reaction zone measurements [20, 21].

A change to 355 nm excitation (Nd:YAG 3rd harmonic) proved to remove a substantial portion of the LIF background, limiting its presence to separate peaks [21]. The current work employed a multipass system aligned at 355 nm, with a schematic of it illustrated in Fig. 1(a). An Nd:YAG laser operating at 10 kHz repetition rate with an average power of 22 W was used as the light source. The beam was guided into the multipass cavity through an $f = 70$ cm focusing lens and a mechanical (Thorlabs ELL14) rotational mount housing a $\lambda/2$ waveplate used to change the laser polarization.

The cavity is created with two 10 cm diameter plano-concave mirrors of focal length $f = 15$ cm, placed 60 cm apart; the laser beam enters the cavity through a hole in one of the mirrors, getting trapped inside for multiple reflections. These reflections produce a beam pattern with two focal points located in the horizontal plane in the middle between the mirrors and roughly 3 mm apart from each other perpendicular to the beam path, as can be seen in Fig. 1(b). For the employed setup, this results in a signal enhancement of around 27 times compared to a single pass of the laser beam. The signal is then collected using two spherical lenses ($f = +200$ mm) to the spectrometer (IsoPlane SCT320, Princeton Instruments) equipped with a grating of 2400 lines/mm and with an ICCD camera (PI-MAX 4, Princeton Instruments) mounted on it. The resolution in the vertical plane was defined by the spectrometer slit set to 150 μm . An additional collection mirror, 75 mm in diameter and focal length $f = +150$ mm, is placed on the opposite side of the collection lenses to double the detected signal.

2.2. Experimental procedure

A porous-plug McKenna burner 6 cm in diameter was placed on a translational mount below the two focal points of the multipass cavity, allowing for height adjustment. The burner was supplied with NH_3 , O_2 and Ar using calibrated mass flow controllers operated with the Flow-View (<https://fluidat.com/>) software. Three flame conditions were studied, as shown in Table 1. The Ar dilution is around 70 % (of the total mixture) for each case.

A stainless steel stagnation plate, positioned 2 cm above the burner

Table 1
 $NH_3/O_2/Ar$ flame compositions.

Equivalence ratio Φ	Ar, nl/ min	O_2 , nl/ min	NH_3 , nl/ min	Inlet velocity (cm/ s)
0.8	10.484	2.273	2.424	9.932
1.0	10.563	1.985	2.647	9.941
1.2	10.332	1.836	2.938	9.883

surface, was used to stabilize the premixed flames in the gap 2.5–5 mm above the burner surface, depending on the equivalence ratio. A water bath (Grant GD120) was used to keep the burner cooling water and plug at a constant temperature of 303 K for additional flame stability.

The height above the burner (HAB) position for Raman spectroscopy measurements was calibrated in two ways. First, the starting and ending points of the measured range were defined by placing a piece of photosensitive paper on the burner surface for registration of laser burn marks. The distance between the two points was divided into 16 steps, with the smallest step corresponding to one-eighth of a turn of the mount handle and a size of ~ 0.35 mm. For the second height calibration, an electronic caliper was attached to the translational mount, and the steps were read out throughout the measurement process. The mismatch between the two methods stayed within 0.02 mm for all cases.

For each HAB position, three pairs of spectra were recorded: the major species range ($900\text{--}4200\text{ cm}^{-1}$), the N_2O range around 1285 cm^{-1} , and the NO range around 1870 cm^{-1} , each taken at vertical and horizontal polarizations of the laser to aid with the background subtraction during the quantification process. Measurements for each equivalence ratio were performed continuously within 2–3 h, with each separate spectrum taking 10–120 s to acquire, depending on the camera settings. In addition, calibration measurements have been performed in a flat premixed laminar stoichiometric $11.276\text{ cm/s N}_2\text{O/CH}_4/\text{Ar}$ flame using the same setup. A more in-depth discussion on the calibration can be found in Section 3. All of the flames were stable throughout the measurement process.

Detailed descriptions of the principles of Raman spectroscopy, as well as its quantification process, are available in the literature [18]. In the present work, quantification followed an established routine: for each species of interest, an integration channel was assigned, and the corresponding cross-section value was determined. Cross-section values for N_2 and O_2 were acquired based on spectral modelling data that was employed for temperature measurements [29] and further compared with experimental values obtained with the present setup. Cross-section values for H_2O , H_2 , N_2O and NO were acquired by calibration measurements, described in further detail in Section 3. Fig. 2 illustrates a spectrum measured in the reaction zone region of an $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flame with the relevant species identified, as well as references to sections of this paper that discuss how some of the complications that arose during the quantification were handled.

3. Calibration measurements and error propagation

The change from 532 to 355 nm in excitation wavelength allows for

Fig. 2. Reaction-zone Raman spectrum of an $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flame taken at vertical laser polarization ($\Phi=0.8$, 1550 K, 355 nm excitation). Positions of the relevant species are noted and numbers represent the sections in which they are further discussed.

removal of the broadband fluorescence background [21]. However, some fluorescence is still present in the form of sharp peaks, as can be seen in Fig. 2, for example, in the range $2500\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (cf. Fig. 2). While recent studies ascertain that NH_2 is the source of fluorescence when excited with a 532 nm laser [30], and also propose ways of handling it [31], to the authors' knowledge, similar research is yet to be performed for the 355 nm excitation. Xin et al. have investigated NH_2 transitions in the ultraviolet regime, and the 355 nm wavelength could induce excitation of the $\tilde{A}^2A_1(0,21,0) \leftarrow X^2B_1(0,0,0)$ transitions [32]. The investigations by Xin et al. were made in cold gas, and the lines assigned in their study do not match the ones observed in the range $2500\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to wavelength interval 390–397 nm [32]. However, spectral simulations based on the data of Xin et al. and for the NH_2 ground state reported by Birss et al. [33] indicate that $\tilde{A}^2A_1(0,19,0) \rightarrow X^2B_1(0,0,0)$ transitions at elevated temperature would reside in this range. Thus, considering the complexity of the NH_2 molecule [17] as well as the change of the spectral shape at higher temperatures due to redistribution of the energy-level populations, NH_2 still remains a realistic candidate. Nevertheless, other alternatives cannot be completely excluded, and as of now, the authors cannot definitely identify the source of fluorescence.

While measurements at orthogonal laser polarizations can be employed to separate vibrational Raman signals from the background [6,18,30], this method could not fully suppress some of the flame zone fluorescence in the present experiment. Though gas-phase LIF signals often get depolarized, it is possible for LIF gas-phase signals to exhibit a dependence on laser polarization [6], which has also been observed experimentally, for example, for OH in flames [34]. Both the NO and N_2O Raman peaks, as well as those of O_2 , have residual fluorescence lines overlapping with them after subtraction of fluorescence background measured at orthogonal polarization. For NO, the overlap only affects the first two measurement points that are located at the end of the reaction zone, which was accounted for by fitting the NO signal to the expected spectral shape, as predicted by PGOPHER [35] simulations that were performed based on molecular data from Miller et al. [36]. The determination of the remaining NO data points as well as peak NO values is not affected by fluorescence.

Since both NH_2 and N_2O are combustion intermediates present in the reaction zone, their overlap persists throughout its whole range, and a similar issue also applies to O_2 . Examples of the residual spectral LIF footprint can be seen in Fig. 4 (for O_2) and in Fig. 6 (for N_2O). Moreover, setup-specific and temperature-dependent data were required for species cross-sections and depolarization ratios, which led to the choice of the calibration flame ($\text{N}_2\text{O/CH}_4/\text{Ar}$). The said flame was chosen for their determination primarily based on the large amounts of N_2O available that would allow for the acquisition of well-defined high-temperature spectral data. CH_4 was selected as a fuel because well-established chemical kinetic mechanisms are available for flame simulations. The calibration flame was employed to acquire:

- Crosstalk-free water spectra to be used as a reference to resolve the $\text{NH}_3\text{--H}_2\text{O}$ crosstalk in the $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames.
- High-temperature fluorescence-free spectra for N_2O to aid with the resolution of the fluorescence overlap.
- High-temperature data for H_2 , H_2O and N_2O for cross-section evaluation.

3.1. $\text{NH}_3\text{--H}_2\text{O}$ overlap

Spectral overlap between lines of NH_3 and H_2O is one of the challenges that have to be faced during the quantification of Raman data from NH_3 flames. The employed evaluation method relies on well-defined spectral shapes of the species for integration of Raman signal intensities. Since both NH_3 and H_2O are major species, proper resolution of the overlap is crucial since any error in the determination of mole

Fig. 3. Reaction zone spectra of the $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames (plot shows $\Phi=1.2$, 1614 K) taken at vertical polarization (blue line) show spectral overlap between Raman peaks of NH_3 and H_2O . After background subtraction of the $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flame spectral data acquired at horizontal polarization (green line) the shape of the water peak can be fitted to a reference H_2O spectrum from the $\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_4/\text{Ar}$ calibration flame (black line). This enables determination of the NH_3 and H_2O integrals separately for concentration evaluation.

fractions of these species can have a noticeable effect on other evaluated concentrations. The H_2O spectra obtained from the $\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_4/\text{Ar}$ calibration flame were matched against the H_2O spectra from the $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames, as demonstrated in Fig. 3. The temperature difference between the spectra was kept within the general uncertainty for temperature measurements. The resulting shape was used to calculate the H_2O integral for the spectra of $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames, while the NH_3 integral was defined as the difference between the total $\text{NH}_3+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ area and the H_2O integral.

3.2. O_2 – handling of fluorescence

Also for O_2 , subtracting a spectrum measured at horizontal polarization from that measured at vertical polarization could not sufficiently suppress the background fluorescence (cf. Fig. 4, bottom right); as a result, a different way of defining the O_2 spectral shape was employed. Similarly, as for N_2 , an O_2 Raman spectrum model was developed based on the data provided in [29]. The model for N_2 has already been calibrated and employed for temperature measurements in our previous studies [21,28]. Since the present calibration flame did not generate an O_2 signal that would be sufficient for temperature fitting, older sets of data obtained in our previous works [21,28] were used to cross-check the present O_2 model against the N_2 model for the temperature evaluation; the obtained values were within ± 50 K for flame temperatures which fits into the overall temperature error margin. Example fits that were used to test the model performance with the data from a laminar premixed $\Phi=0.8$ NH_3/Air flame (532 nm excitation) can be seen in Fig. 4 (upper row).

Fig. 4. Upper row: example temperature fits for O_2 and N_2 taken at the same HAB in an 0.8 NH_3/Air flame. Lower row: example temperature fits for O_2 and N_2 taken at the same HAB in a 1.2 $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flame. Spectrum obtained after subtraction of a background acquired at horizontal polarization shows residual fluorescence, e.g. the peak at 1490 cm^{-1} , overlapping with the O_2 Raman signal.

Table 2
Definitions of the error margins.

Species	H ₂ O	N ₂	O ₂	H ₂	NH ₃	NO	N ₂ O
Cross-section	5	5	5	5	8	10	15
Integration limits	5	5	5	5	5	10	5
LIF background	–	–	7	–	–	–	10–17 %
Depolarization rescaling	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total (rounded up)	8	8	10	8	10	15	20–23 %

Since both O₂ and N₂ are recorded at the same flame height in the NH₃/O₂/Ar flames, the temperature predictions from each species should yield results that agree within the uncertainty. However, the direct fit of the O₂ spectra over the experimental profile for the NH₃/O₂/Ar flame did not result in similar temperature estimations (Fig. 4, right bottom row, red dashed line), most likely due to the residual fluorescence footprint distorting the spectral shape of O₂. Thus, the O₂ modelling was performed using the linewidth and temperature values obtained from the N₂ data for the same flame conditions as an input, then rescaled based on the intensity of the O₂ Q-branch $\nu = 1 \leftarrow \nu = 0$ transition (Fig. 4, right bottom row, black dashed line), providing an O₂ spectrum that was used for concentration evaluation. The error introduced by the rescaling was estimated as the difference between rescaling against the vertically polarized spectrum and the spectrum obtained after background subtraction at horizontal polarization and was added to the O₂ error bar, as summarized in Section 3.4, Table 2.

3.3. N₂O measurements

3.3.1. Cross-section

The initial aim was to acquire temperature-dependent spectra for N₂O that would aid data quantification. However, it was discovered that the present setup could not spectrally resolve the N₂O hot bands; moreover, the modelling of the molecule also posed certain difficulties, primarily due to the lack of data on polarizability matrix elements, as also brought up by Lill et al. [25]. Thus, instead of acquiring a higher accuracy cross-section from simulations, as for N₂ and O₂, the authors chose to estimate the error the cross-section temperature dependence introduces based on available data.

The estimation was based on comparing mole fraction values of oxidizer N₂O for this particular flame acquired from different sources. The first source is predictions of kinetic models, and the second source is based on experimental values evaluated using a room-temperature N₂O cross-section. In theory, the Raman signal for a given setup and species depends only on the species mole fraction, the gas density related to temperature and the temperature-dependent cross-section [6]. Thus, from simulated mole fractions and temperatures, it is possible to obtain a profile corresponding to the N₂O Raman signal for a constant cross-section value to be compared with experimental data. The observed slope mismatch between the two should be attributed to the temperature-dependent cross-section change and could be used to estimate the degree to which it can affect the quantification.

However, the described routine posed several challenges. First, it relies on simulations to provide the mole fraction data. To estimate the error possibly introduced by that, several models from different research groups were compared, i.e., [37–39]. The resulting predictions for N₂O mole fractions and temperature, two parameters that were used for the cross-section evaluation, can be seen in Fig. 5(a) and appear to be in good agreement. Second, depending on the N₂O gradient in the flame zone, even a minor shift in height can result in a major change in mole fraction, so for comparison between simulations and experimental data, one would have to introduce an additional uncertainty to account for that. Third, to be able to compare simulation and experimental N₂O mole fraction values, the datasets would have to be matched against each other. In the present case, this was done based on matching the corresponding temperatures. However, a strong fluorescence signal

from CN (identified based on a LIFBASE [40] simulation) was observed for the experimental data which interfered with the N₂ signal for spectra acquired in the reaction zone, making most reaction-zone data unsuitable for temperature evaluation with the fitting method that was employed throughout the work. Instead, the experimental temperature profile was recovered based on a combination of signal decrease due to decreasing gas density in the preheat zone and evaluation of LIF-free N₂ spectra measured at the starting and ending points of the reaction zone (Fig. 5(b)). Since what matters are the temperature and N₂O mole fraction gradients against HAB that are related to the reaction zone width and not its position against HAB, the profiles can be shifted to match each other.

As mentioned above, precise height determination plays a crucial role when matching the two datasets. With the general step for measurements in the flame being around 0.35 mm, the worst-case error margin was estimated as ± 0.05 mm. Then, the two datasets were shifted against each other within 0.05 mm; the resulting ratios between modeling predictions and experiment can be seen in Fig. 5(c). This ratio corresponds to the temperature dependence of the N₂O Raman cross-section. The observed mole-fraction deviation was approximately 17 % for the temperature at which the N₂O mole fraction peaks in the NH₃/O₂/Ar flames (~ 1700 K) for all three models. After varying the cross-section within the established bounds, the final N₂O mole fraction error margin for the NH₃/O₂/Ar flame was fixed at 15 % (see Section 3.4, Table 2). The degree of error estimated with the present method also seems to be in agreement with the extrapolated data for the N₂O cross-section from the oven measurements reported by Lill et al. [25], where it appears to be within 20 % for the relevant temperature range.

3.3.2. Handling of fluorescence

Similar to the O₂ case, a residual background fluorescence footprint overlapped with the N₂O Raman data. Two different methods were then employed to acquire N₂O species mole fractions: the first method was based on the evaluation of the equivalence ratio-dependent relative integral value of the combined N₂O+LIF peaks against pure LIF peaks, and in the second method the original shape of the N₂O Raman peaks was recovered by subtracting the LIF footprint from the N₂O+LIF peak. The following section provides clarification on the abovementioned routines.

Method one: First, to establish the exact N₂O peak position and shape, high-temperature N₂O spectra were acquired from the N₂O/CH₄/Ar calibration flame, and the rough initial mole-fraction estimation was performed by spectrally matching (as in, rescaling the reference N₂O spectrum as high as possible so that it would still fit within the boundary of the N₂O+LIF peak without distorting the spectral shape) them against the data from the NH₃/O₂/Ar flames. Fig. 6(a), dashed lines, illustrates such conditions for all three equivalence ratios. However, that only provides a possible maximum value of the N₂O fraction which can only be used as a starting point for the evaluation. The evaluation was then performed as follows: for each equivalence ratio, relative intensities for six LIF pure peaks (labelled in Fig. 6, (c)) were studied, and the peak overlapping with N₂O was the only one to exhibit a dependence on the set equivalence ratio (Fig. 6, (b), crosses), with pure LIF peaks being consistent against each other for different values of Φ within a 5–10 % deviation. Fig. 6(b), squares, provides an example of such a dependence for a ratio between two of the six pure LIF peaks, with each point being an average of four data points with the highest measured N₂O fractions in the flame and of different temperature in the range 1300–1900 K, and the error bar representing the standard deviation between them. Thus, the error bar includes variations in temperature. If NH₂ is the source of fluorescence, this is in line with the predictions of the models employed in the present study, since NH₂ concentrations stay constant within 1000 ± 100 ppm across all models and all equivalence ratios (Fig. S1). Having established that, the N₂O portion of the signal was then estimated through an iteration process: first, the initial maximum N₂O integral evaluated with the spectral overlap was subtracted from the total

Fig. 5. a) Comparison between N_2O mole fraction vs. temperature predictions of the three kinetic models. b) Temperature profiles for CH_4+N_2O+Ar calibration flame. Experimental values (circles) compared with simulations (lines). c) Ratio between N_2O mole fraction modelling predictions [37] and experimental data evaluated using a room-temperature N_2O cross-section value. The graph represents the temperature dependence of the N_2O cross-section.

N_2O+LIF area, and the relative equivalence ratio dependence was studied again. Since the Φ dependence comes from the N_2O signal, proper subtraction for all of the cases should remove it, meaning that the resulting values should form a horizontal line in Fig. 6, (b). Given the rather rough first estimation, this was not the case for the first iteration: instead of the horizontal dependence, the values on the lean side were lower than on the rich side, meaning that the N_2O fraction was overestimated. The expected N_2O integral was then reduced and the dependence against Φ was studied again, with several iterations ultimately leading to the values in Fig. 6, (b), circles, which correspond to the evaluated N_2O mole fraction. During that procedure, the pure reference LIF spectra (e.g., Fig. 6(a), red line) were identified in a manner similar to the way the maximum N_2O contribution was estimated: this time, instead of rescaling the reference N_2O spectra to fit inside the combined peak without distorting the spectral shape, the temperature dependent shape of the combined peak was studied to find a spectrum for which the gap between the two peaks (located around 1278 cm^{-1}) would be as close as possible to zero – meaning that it would be once again impossible to fit the expected N_2O peak inside without distorting the shape. The peak of this spectrum was then considered to contain no detectable N_2O contribution and represent a pure LIF signal. The integral of that “pure” LIF peak was then fixed as the reference “zero” value with N_2O absent. Ultimately, the error to which the “ N_2O

fraction” of the peak could be estimated was limited by the relative LIF peak ratios for varying Φ and resulted in around 10 % uncertainty for the final mole fraction determination.

Method two: in the second method, the shape of the N_2O Raman signal was recovered and integrated directly in order to obtain the resulting mole fraction values. The shape of the background LIF peak used for subtraction was obtained from spectra measured at the edge of the reaction zone where the expected N_2O values evaluated with the first method should be below 200 ppm. Then, the temperature-dependent intensity changes were studied for the same six pure LIF peaks (Fig. 6, (c)), with the resulting values for different peaks being consistent with each other within 5%. The normalized average of these values was then employed to rescale the original LIF peak used for subtraction from the N_2O+LIF area. The resulting N_2O spectra for the heights corresponding to the peak N_2O concentrations for each equivalence ratio are presented in Fig. 7.

The comparison between the resulting mole fraction predictions of the two methods can be seen in the Results section (Fig. 12). While the first method might appear more convoluted, the authors believe that it provides more reliable data given that its evaluation relies on reference spectra and rescaling only for the initial guess, and the acquired values are therefore obtained purely from the particular heights of the relevant flame. The second method, while more straightforward in the procedure

Fig. 6. a) Sample spectra used for N_2O evaluation at its maximum position for three different $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flame conditions (solid lines), an N_2O spectrum of similar temperature from a $\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_4/\text{Ar}$ calibration flame rescaled to provide the corresponding initial guesses for the first method (dashed lines), as well as a reference LIF spectrum from the edge of the reaction zone defined as the pure LIF peak (red solid line) b) Three different peak ratios plotted against Φ , illustrating the dependence of the LIF+ N_2O peak intensity (crosses) on the equivalence ratio. Comparison against LIF background that remains constant at different equivalence ratios (squares) allows for estimation of LIF contribution to the LIF+ N_2O signal (circles) and N_2O concentration evaluation. c) Reaction-zone Raman spectrum taken at vertical laser polarization ($\Phi=0.8$, 1550 K, 355 nm excitation) with the relevant LIF peaks highlighted.

Fig. 7. The original $\text{N}_2\text{O}+\text{LIF}$ Raman spectra for the three equivalence ratios at 1784, 1716 and 1749 K, the LIF background used for subtraction, the resulting spectra after the subtraction and the experimental N_2O spectra from $\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_4/\text{Ar}$ 1735 K calibration flame used as a reference to ascertain the subtraction.

itself, was much more challenging to perform in practice given the low spectral resolution of the initial data and limited pure LIF spectra that could be used as a reference, which led to somewhat higher values for the experimental uncertainty.

3.4. Closing remarks on error propagation

Final estimations for experimental uncertainties can be found in Table 2. Since the uncertainties arise from different sources, and since in

the present quantification routine derived concentrations of each species affect those of other species, the overall error introduced was estimated based on a relative change to the final mole fraction value of each species.

Post-flame data from the calibration flame were used to acquire high-temperature cross-sections for H₂O and H₂. NH₃ and NO cross-sections were initially acquired through cold gas calibrations. The high-temperature cross-section for NO was determined in our previous work [21] by seeding NO into a lean CH₄/air flame. The cross-section appeared to stay constant within the experimental uncertainty (10 %), thus, the same value was used for NO in this study. Rounded room-temperature cross-section values employed in the present work can be found in Table 3.

Due to the overall low signal of NO and its spectrum being distributed across multiple vibrational bands, the choice of integration limits was not as straightforward as for other species, resulting in a higher error margin. While subtracting data acquired with different polarizations was used to filter the Raman signal, setting horizontal polarization does not always actually suppress the entire Raman signal, meaning that a portion of the signal is lost during subtraction. Therefore, additional data analysis was performed to obtain effective depolarization ratios for different species at relevant temperatures, which were then employed to rescale the signal back to its full value. This added another source of error.

Lastly, because the multipass setup is sensitive to changes in optical density due to rising temperature, some of the recorded datasets exhibited significant shot-to-shot variations in intensity, especially in the preheat zone. However, in all of the cases, averaging was employed to ensure that the data would converge to a constant value. The settings at which that occurred were established prior to the measurements and varied depending on the position in the flame, the overall variation is within 60,000 to 400,000 single-shot frames. Thus, the standard deviation between averaged frames was not considered as one of the sources of error.

4. Modeling details

All the flame structure simulations, as well as sensitivity analysis, were performed using the Premixed Laminar Burner-Stabilized Stagnation Flame model, in ANSYS Chemkin 2020 R2 software (<https://www.ansys.com/>). The problem type was defined as Solve Gas Energy Equation, with thermal diffusion effect and mixture-averaged transport considered. Depending on the employed detailed kinetic model and the corresponding stiffness of convergence, the GRAD parameter was set to 0.02–0.23, and CURV was set to 0.05–0.3, resulting in a total of 100–600 grid points. The temperature boundaries were set at 303 K on the burner surface and 1050 K at the surface of the stagnation plate.

Nowadays, many different kinetic models for ammonia combustion are available in the literature, as reviewed recently by Szanthoffer et al. [41]. Using a large dataset of experimental results and calculating the averaged error of model predictions relative to these experimental data, the authors [41] concluded that for NH₃/H₂ fuel mixtures, the best-performing models are POLIMI-2020 [42], Han-2020 [43] and KAUST-2021 [4]. Therefore, these three models will be compared with the experimental results obtained in the present study. Meanwhile, advanced works were published on the rate constants for N₂H₂ chemistry [44–47], NH₂O chemistry [48], NH₂+NO₂ [49], and third-body collisional efficiencies of H₂O and NH₃ [50], promoting the understanding of key reactions in NH₃ oxidation and pyrolysis. Therefore, the authors' group proposed an updated kinetic model [51], which was

Table 3
Relative room-temperature cross-section values.

Species	H ₂ O	N ₂	O ₂	H ₂	NH ₃	NO	N ₂ O
Cross-section	2.2	1	1.3	2.4	7.2	0.4	2.8

based on the model suggested in the study of NH₃/O₂/Ar flames [52] adopting the results of N₂H₂ and NH₂O reactions [44,46,48], and third-body collisional efficiency of NH₃ and H₂O [50]. It was found that the improved model [51] gives good predictions for various NH₃ flames at different conditions. In the present work, a new model is developed based on the previous one [51], with updated rate constants from the N₂O chemistry [53,54]. This model, which in the following will be referred as Konnov-2024, has overall good performance for NH₃ flames and ignition delay times as shown in the Supplementary Material (SM) in Fig. S2–3, therefore, it is also compared with the present experiments. Specific modifications introduced in the present model compared to the previous version [51] are outlined in the SM as well.

The present model included the Planck Mean Absorption Coefficients for species H₂O, NH₃, NO, and N₂O to account for radiation heat loss, the same as in the previous version of the model [51]. These coefficients were initially taken from the study of Nakamura and Shindo [55], who found that radiation heat loss affected the 1-D planar flame structure of ammonia and air mixtures. The Planck Mean Absorption Coefficients are compatible with Chemkin-Pro's thermodynamic data file format, and thus can be adopted by Chemkin-Pro to approximate the radiative heat loss modeled by the optically thin model. It was found that considering that radiative heat loss has negligible effects on most of the speciation peaks, but it has a minor impact on the product zone temperature profiles and the flame positions. Details will be discussed in the results section. The three chemical kinetic models selected from literature do not include radiative species, therefore, the modeling results from these models are considered without including radiative heat loss to simplify the discussion. While comparing models with differing assumptions about radiation is not ideal, it reflects the real performance of the models. Moreover, the effect of radiative heat loss is minimal and does not impact the overall conclusions regarding the models' accuracy.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Experimental results

Fig. 8 shows the vertical temperature profiles for three NH₃/O₂/Ar flame conditions. The temperature was retrieved by fitting theoretical spectra simulated with PGOPHER [35] to experimental N₂ spectra. The routine has previously been tested against the data obtained from the work of Utsav and Varghese [26] and operates on the basis of the Raman spectrum changing shape with temperature: as more vibrational levels get populated, "hot bands" appear. Thus, the spectral shape of the peak illustrates the temperature-dependent distribution of the energy-level population and can be used to extract temperature data. The sources of uncertainty of the present temperature evaluation routine are discussed in our previous works [21,28]. However, since the shape of the peak exhibits only minor changes for temperatures below 500 K, evaluation of temperatures in that range appears to pose a challenge to the present methodology, as can be seen with the first several points of the lean case. Thus, a bigger error margin was introduced for lower temperatures.

Also shown in Fig. 8 are the temperature profiles calculated using the four tested kinetic models. While the model predictions show good agreement with the experimental values when it comes to the maximum temperature, the four examined models predict different positions of the reaction zone, indicated by the temperature gradient, due to their different predictions for the laminar burning velocity (LBV). As shown in SM Fig. S4, the simulated LBV at $\Phi=1$ is compared using four models. Models predicting lower LBV are associated with a higher distance of the flame reaction zone from the burner, as seen in Fig. 8. Some differences can also be observed in the predictions of the product zone temperature drop profile. This could be a consequence of an uncertain stagnation plate temperature evaluation, which was performed with a thermocouple due to the limitations in accessing the position close to the plate. Nevertheless, variation of the stagnation plate temperature in the

Fig. 8. Temperature change with HAB for $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames. Experimental values (symbols) compared with simulations (lines).

modelling does not affect the calculated profiles of N_2O and NO .

Figs. 9 and 10 illustrate major species mole fractions plotted against HAB for the three studied flame conditions. Note that the spatial scale in Figs. 9–11 is from 0 to 15 mm to improve visibility. Predictions of the four kinetic models qualitatively and quantitatively agree with the measurements both in terms of the gradients and of the major species concentrations in the fresh mixture and the products, and the observed mismatch with the modelling is primarily due to the differences in burning velocity predictions. The shift of the calculated profiles between models reflects the shift of the temperature profiles seen in Fig. 8 and discussed above. All four models predict almost coinciding major species concentrations in the regions where concentration gradients vanish.

It should be noted that for rich conditions, H_2O diffused back to the preheat zone because the flame was stabilized close to the burner. This affects the initial concentrations evaluated at positions of lower temperature, but is resolved for heights where N_2O and NO concentrations peak. Thus, it should not introduce an additional source of error to minor species mole fraction determination.

Remaining discrepancies between simulations and measurements, therefore, may indicate additional experimental uncertainties not fully accounted for. In the present case, the most likely cause for that would be a weak residual fluorescence signal that could possibly overlap with N_2 , H_2O or NH_3 . While it is not strong enough to introduce visible changes to the overall spectral shape, smaller-scale contributions, if present, could still lead to a slight overestimation of the spectral shape used for integration. Another source of error is relevant to the reactant zone – for the first two or three points for all the measurements height

fluctuations of the multi-pass arrangement were observed. While, as mentioned in Section 3.4, this was handled with increased averaging, it is possible that for some extreme cases, the averaging was not performed sufficiently, which is manifested in, e.g. the second point above the burner surface for NH_3 and O_2 in the lean case.

Figs. S5–6 in the SM present the mole fractions of the major species (NH_3 , O_2 , H_2O , H_2 , and N_2) plotted against temperature. This approach minimizes the influence of positional differences in the reaction zone. Figures show that the model predictions converge well, accurately capturing the measurements for both the product zone and the reaction zone. Discrepancies from the experimental data are primarily observed in the preheat zone (the first 3–4 points above 303 K). These discrepancies further highlight the challenges with handling data in that region, as mentioned before: first, the temperature estimation is difficult up until the temperatures at which the first hot band gets populated; second, strong oscillations of the multipass system have been observed in that region that possibly did not get sufficiently averaged; third, for the rich flame, H_2O diffused back to the preheat zone, affecting mole fraction evaluation in the lower-temperature region. However, since all these issues get resolved at around ~ 1200 K and each height is quantified independently, they should not play a notable role in minor species evaluation.

Compared with minor species such as NO , N_2O and, to a degree, H_2 , the behavior of the most abundant species (O_2 , NH_3 , N_2 , H_2O) of reactants and products is well determined, and all simulation mechanisms agree within 1%. Thus, validation against these data is not the purpose of the present study, and the major species are used as a tool for

Fig. 9. NH_3 , O_2 , and H_2O mole fractions change with HAB for $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames. Experimental values (symbols) compared with predictions of the four kinetic models (lines).

quantification of the minor species. The observed discrepancies between experimental results and modelling predictions only affected the concentrations evaluated for minor species N_2O and NO within the error margins previously established in Section 3.4, which was considered sufficient for the minor species quantification.

Fig. 11 shows the measured NO mole fraction profiles compared with predictions of the tested mechanisms. The concentrations exhibit the expected dependence on the equivalence ratio, having higher maximum value at leaner conditions, as well as the qualitative behavior: for lean and stoichiometric cases, the concentration reaches a plateau in the product zone, whereas, for the rich case, the NO is fully consumed. Even though the NO mole fraction is around 2–3 times higher than that of N_2O , its Raman cross-section being several times lower results in a higher detection limit (around 600 ppm, defined as the concentration corresponding to a 2:1 signal-to-noise ratio), which is most critical for measurements in the rich case where the peak values only go up to 1000 ppm. Nevertheless, the peak mole fraction values can provide a point of reference for the modeling.

Fig. 12 presents N_2O mole fraction profiles in the three flames with experimental values estimated with the two LIF subtraction methods. The two datasets appear to agree within the experimental error. However, for the rich case, it can be clearly observed that the second method predicts higher N_2O mole fractions, which could be a consequence of the spectral averaging performed with noise levels mixed in for the lower N_2O values. While a higher cross-section value results in an overall higher signal as compared with NO , the uncertainty to which LIF overlap could be resolved limits the detection threshold. Thus, the detection limit was estimated to be around 500 ppm. Similar to NO , the species follow the expected dependence on the equivalence ratio, being more abundant in lean conditions and least abundant in rich conditions and being present only in the reaction zone. In both Figs. 11 and 12, the agreement with the models varies across the cases for both flame position and maximum concentration. Note that in both cases points corresponding to values below the detection limit are only presented as a part of the overall profile and thus have no error bars attached. Further discussion of the model performance is presented in the next section.

Fig. 10. N_2 and H_2 mole fractions change with HAB for $NH_3/O_2/Ar$ flames. Experimental values (symbols) compared with predictions of the four kinetic models (lines).

In Fig 11 and 12, the KAUST-2021 model captures the peak concentration of N_2O best but overpredicts the NO peak at the fuel-lean side. Both the Konnov-2024 and POLIMI-2020 mechanisms over-predict the N_2O peak concentration, but the POLIMI-2020 model gives better predictions for NO . The Han-2020 model fails to predict the N_2O peak at fuel-lean conditions and also did not predict NO well. Figure S7 in the SM shows NO and N_2O mole fractions plotted against temperature, confirming that the KAUST-2021 model demonstrates the best overall performance for both NO and N_2O profiles.

Overall, the differences between experimental data and selected models are within 25 % for NO , but are up to 50 % for N_2O . Considering the experimental uncertainties, most of the models tested give acceptable predictions for the NO profiles.

Comparisons using Konnov-2024 with and without considering radiation heat loss are shown in the SM Fig. S8. It was found that accounting for radiative heat loss reduced the maximum flame temperature by approximately 46 K, 50 K, and 36 K at $\Phi=0.8$, 1.0 and 1.2, respectively. It also resulted in a 0.5 mm shift in the flame reaction-zone position across all equivalence ratios. For the fuel-lean and stoichiometric conditions, this shift slightly improved the flame position, whereas for the fuel-rich case, it had the opposite effect. Considering radiative heat loss had a negligible impact on the predicted peak values and profiles of the major species: NH_3 , O_2 , H_2O , and N_2 , as well as the intermediate species (N_2O). However, it led to a slight reduction in the mole fraction of NO in the product zone by 3 %, 4.2 %, and 6 % at $\Phi=0.8$, 1.0, and 1.2, respectively, due to the suppression of thermal NO formation at reduced temperatures. Similarly, the peak mole fraction of H_2 was reduced by 3 %, 2.4 %, and 5.4 % at $\Phi=0.8$, 1.0, and 1.2, respectively, due to the suppression of the thermal decomposition of NH_3 at a lower flame temperature. In general, radiative heat loss does not significantly influence the accuracy of model evaluations.

5.2. Analysis of the models

Previous studies on the NO_x chemistry indicate that N_2O in ammonia flames is primarily generated from NO through the direct pathway $NO+NH=N_2O+H$ or via the indirect pathway $NO\rightarrow NO_2\rightarrow N_2O$, involving the reactions $NO+HO_2=NO_2+H$ followed by $NO_2+NH_2=N_2O+H_2O$ [3,56]. Given that NO predictions in the four models outperform those for N_2O in the present flames, it suggests that differences in the $NO-N_2O$ pathway interaction chemistry or the N_2O subset chemistry among the models may contribute to the variations in N_2O predictions.

To investigate this, kinetic analyses were conducted using the Konnov-2024 and KAUST-2021 models. Rate-of-production (ROP) analysis, shown in Fig. 13 at stoichiometric conditions, reveals that in both models, the reaction $NO+NH=N_2O+H$ (or its equivalent reverse reaction $N_2O+H=NO+NH$ in Konnov-2024) is the sole pathway for N_2O formation within the reaction zone. Once formed, N_2O is predominantly consumed through the reaction $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ and the third-body dissociation reaction $N_2O(+M)=N_2+O(+M)$.

Sensitivity analysis further highlights the importance of the aforementioned reactions. However, not all of these reactions are equally significant across the models. Results calculated under stoichiometric conditions using the Konnov-2024 and KAUST-2021 models are provided in the SM (Fig S9). In the Konnov-2024 model, the N_2O consumption reaction $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ is the primary factor influencing N_2O reduction, while the N_2O formation reaction $N_2O+H=NO+NH$ (proceeding in the reverse direction) is considered not crucial for overall N_2O prediction. Instead, reactions that impact NO and NH concentrations are more important for accurate N_2O modeling. In contrast, in the KAUST-2021 model, the N_2O consumption reaction $N_2O+H=NO+NH$ is less important, but $N_2O(+M)=N_2+O(+M)$ is sensitive in reducing N_2O ,

Fig. 11. NO mole fraction change with HAB for $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames. Experimental values (circles) compared with predictions of the four kinetic models (lines).

Fig. 12. N_2O change with HAB for $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ flames. Experimental values (circles) compared with predictions of the four kinetic models (lines).

Fig. 13. ROP analysis of N_2O using the KAUST-2021 and Konnov-2024 models for simulations of the stoichiometric $NH_3/O_2/Ar$ flame. Negative ROP values indicate reactions that consume N_2O .

and the formation reaction $NH+NO=N_2O+H$ is also sensitive affecting N_2O concentration.

These findings prove the significance of $NO-N_2O$ pathway reactions and the N_2O subset chemistry in influencing N_2O formation and consumption. Nevertheless, the Konnov-2024 and KAUST-2021 models utilize different sources for the rate constants of the N_2O+H branches and $N_2O(+M)=N_2+O(+M)$. A comparison of the rate constants for the reactions $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ and $N_2O+H=NO+NH$ are provided in the SM Fig. S10, showing that the rate constant for $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ in the KAUST-2021 model is around 2 times higher than in the Konnov-2024 model. Due to the high sensitivity of $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ in the Konnov-2024 model, accommodating the rate constants of this reaction using the same source as the KAUST-2021 model significantly reduces the predicted N_2O concentration, and aligning it closely with experimental data under all the investigated conditions, as shown in the SM Fig S11. However, this adjustment also reduces flame reactivity, as indicated by the upward shift in the reaction zone position.

The KAUST-2021 model adopted the rate constants of $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ from Powell et al. [57], while the Konnov-2024 model adopted rate constants from Klippenstein et al. [58], as discussed in our previous work [59]. This selection was made since reaction $N_2O+H=N_2+OH$ is

also sensitive, affecting the reactivity of $NH_3/N_2O/Air$ and $N_2O/H_2/Ar$ flames [57]. In the Konnov-2024 model, we have incorporated the latest advanced rate constant data, successfully reproducing results across various flames and conditions, as demonstrated in Fig. S2. Further refinements to the Konnov-2024 model regarding N_2O predictions will be made, taking into account the most recent analysis of Glarborg et al. [60], which is, however, left beyond the scope of the present study. One should also note that the KAUST-2021 model is not perfect, it under-predicts the overall flame reactivity both in the present flames, and the $NH_3/O_2/(40-50\%) Ar$ flames studied by Chen et al. [51] illustrated in the SM Fig. S12.

Summarizing the behavior of the four kinetic mechanisms tested and compared with the present flame structure measurements, one may conclude that the major differences are observed in the predictions of NO and N_2O profiles, while predictions of the main species shown in Figs. 9 and 10 are satisfactory. This conclusion, however, contradicts the observations of Osipova et al. [3,5], as illustrated below. The flame structure data from Osipova et al. [5] at $\Phi=1$, 1 atm, and unburnt mixture temperature of 368 K, are compared with predictions of the

Fig. 14. Flame profiles of N_2O and H_2 from Osipova et al. [5] (symbols) compared with predictions of the four investigated kinetic models (lines) at $\Phi=1$, 1 atm, 368 K. Mole fraction of $NH_3=0.222$, $O_2=0.167$, and $Ar=0.611$. The experimental temperature profile was used as simulation input.

same four models. Simulations were carried out adopting the experimental temperature profile provided in their work [5]. The comparison is shown in Fig. 14 for H₂ and N₂O profiles, while comparisons for NH₃, O₂, N₂, H₂O and NO are displayed in Fig. S13 in the SM.

Since the flame front position in the modelling is constrained by the experimental temperature profile, all models yield almost coinciding maxima positions or gradients. However, one may observe systematic overprediction by all mechanisms of the H₂ measurements from Osipova et al. [5], contradicting model performances in Fig. 10. Moreover, all the models, including KAUST-2021, also over-predict the N₂O profiles, while in Fig. 12, the KAUST-2021 model performs well for the present flames considering the uncertainty bars. The divergence in model performances suggests potential data inconsistencies, possibly arising from the differences in experimental methodologies since Osipova et al. [5] utilized an intrusive diagnostic method, in which the flames were sampled with a quartz sonic probe and unavoidable heat losses require information on the temperature profiles from the same experiments.

6. Conclusions

An experimental setup that enables studies of intermediate species in premixed laminar NH₃ flames has been developed, and its applicability has been confirmed by the successful detection (500 ppm detection limit) and quantification of N₂O, as well as the characterization of other species, including NO, and flame temperature. The signal enhancement provided by the multipass setup played a crucial role, allowing the reduction of accumulation by up to 30 times. As a result, measurements at each HAB took around 5 min instead of 2.5 h, which would not appear realistic both in terms of the time required to do a height scan for a single flame, as well as other experimental challenges, such as guaranteeing flame and laser stability throughout the whole measurement process.

Several limitations were identified during the data analysis process, such as the necessity for a higher resolution spectrometer for improved N₂O characterization, as well as the need to identify the source of fluorescence to learn its exact footprint. In the future, this should allow for a significant reduction in the experimental uncertainties.

Lastly, the datasets obtained were compared with predictions of four recent kinetic models, and an analysis of their performance was performed. While most of the models tested give acceptable predictions for the NO profiles, only predictions of the KAUST-2021 model agreed with the N₂O experimental values within the established error margins. The observed differences in N₂O concentration predictions suggest the need for further studies on N₂O chemistry in ammonia flames.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alsu Zubairova: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Jundie Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation. **Alexander A. Konnov:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization. **Christian Brackmann:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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